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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF INTRAVENOUS AND SUBCUTANEOUS
MONOCLONAL ANTIBODIES IN THE TREATMENT OF
ASTHMA**¹Muhammed Ameer Hamzah, ²Anam Sohail, ³Faisal Shahbaz¹Avicenna Teaching hospital, Lahore; ²Hameed Latif hospital, Lahore;³Tehsil Head Quarter Civil Hospital Daska, Sialkot.**Article Received:** July 2019**Accepted:** August 2019**Published:** September 2019**Abstract:**

Introduction: Asthma is an inflammatory chronic disease of multifactorial aetiology, including allergic asthma, which is characterized by eosinophilic airway inflammation, often sustained by allergic sensitization.

Objectives of the study: The main objective of the study is to analyze the use of intravenous and subcutaneous monoclonal antibodies in the treatment of asthma.

Methodology of the study: This study was conducted in Avicenna Teaching hospital, Lahore during January 2019 to July 2019. Male or female allergic asthmatics aged 12 to 75 years who were symptomatic despite treatment with ICSs were eligible if they met the following criteria: duration of asthma, ≥ 1 year; positive immediate responses on skin prick testing to at least 1 common allergen.

Results: Additionally, health-related quality of life was measured using SGRQ. At Week 24, there was a statistically significant improvement in the mean SGRQ score for mepolizumab compared with placebo: -5.8 (95% CI: -10.6, -1.0; $P=0.019$).

Conclusion: It is concluded that omalizumab is effective and safe in patients with severe allergic asthma who experience poor disease control or exacerbations despite recommended therapy.

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INTRODUCTION:

IgE plays a central role in the pathogenesis of allergic diseases. After sensitization, atopic patients respond to allergen exposure through a number of IgE-dependent mechanisms. By forming complexes with free IgE, mAbs against IgE block the interaction between IgE and mast cells and basophils. Thus, the use of anti-IgE mAbs is considered to be a promising approach for the treatment of allergic conditions such as asthma¹.

Asthma is an inflammatory chronic disease of multifactorial aetiology, including allergic asthma, which is characterized by eosinophilic airway inflammation, often sustained by allergic sensitization. Asthma is typically associated with bronchial hyper-responsiveness to direct and indirect triggers. Severe asthma is defined as asthma that requires high-dose inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) plus a second controller (usually a long-acting β_2 agonist [LABA]) and/or systemic corticosteroids for adequate control, or which is uncontrolled despite this high-intensity treatment. An estimated 5–10% of all patients with asthma are believed to have severe refractory asthma².

For patients with severe uncontrolled asthma, four monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) against immunoglobulin E (IgE) or interleukin (IL)-5 are available for clinical use by either subcutaneous (SC) or intravenous (IV) administration as an add-on to ICS plus LABA therapy. The anti-IgE antibody omalizumab has been available for SC use in the USA since 2003 and has also been approved in Europe since 2009. The anti-IL-5 antibodies mepolizumab and benralizumab for SC administration and reslizumab for IV administration were approved in 2015, 2017 and 2016, respectively, in both the USA and Europe³.

According to the Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA) 2017 guidelines, add-on therapy with omalizumab should be considered in patients aged ≥ 6 years with severe allergic asthma, while mepolizumab and reslizumab may be beneficial in patients with severe eosinophilic asthma aged ≥ 12 years. However, it is important to note that reslizumab has only been approved for adults (≥ 18 years)⁴.

mAbs are made of two identical heavy and light chains held together by disulphide bonds at the hinge region to form a Y-shaped structure. They were first created as mouse mAbs using hybridoma technology, but to minimise the immunogenic mouse components, murine mAbs were replaced by chimeric, humanised

and then fully human mAbs. The pharmacokinetics (PK) of mAbs is characterised by low distribution to the extravascular compartment, because of their large molecular size and long elimination half-life ($t_{1/2}$), which depends on slow intracellular catabolism, with no urinary excretion⁵.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The main objective of the study is to analyze the use of intravenous and subcutaneous monoclonal antibodies in the treatment of asthma.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This study was conducted in Avicenna Teaching hospital, Lahore during January 2019 to July 2019. Male or female allergic asthmatics aged 12 to 75 years who were symptomatic despite treatment with ICSs were eligible if they met the following criteria: duration of asthma, ≥ 1 year; positive immediate responses on skin prick testing to at least 1 common allergen. This was a double-blinded, placebo-controlled, multicenter, parallel-group trial. On entry into the study, each patient was switched from his or her currently prescribed ICS to an equivalent dose of BDP. At the end of the second week of the 4- to 6-week run-in period, the dose of BDP was adjusted upward or downward to maintain previous asthma control. The patients were monitored to ensure both the presence of asthma symptoms at levels acceptable to the patients and investigators and patient safety. Serum samples were taken at baseline and before dosing at weeks 16 and 24 to determine IgE concentrations. In omalizumab-treated subjects, serum IgE comprised free IgE and IgE bound to omalizumab.

Statistical analysis: The data was collected and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. All the values were expressed in mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The level of confidence interval is 90 and 95 in this table for the significant value. Additionally, health-related quality of life was measured using SGRQ. At Week 24, there was a statistically significant improvement in the mean SGRQ score for mepolizumab compared with placebo: -5.8 (95% CI: -10.6, -1.0; $P=0.019$). At Week 2, the proportion of subjects with a clinically meaningful decrease in SGRQ score (defined as a decrease of at least 4 units from baseline) was greater for mepolizumab (58%, 40/69) compared with placebo (41%, 27/66).

Table 01: Results of the primary and secondary endpoints in the Intent to treat population

	Number (%) of Subjects	
	Mepolizumab (100 mg SC) N= 69	Placebo
Primary Endpoint:		
Percent Reduction in OCS from Baseline at Weeks 20-24 (%)		
N		
90% - 100%		
75% - <90%	12 (17%)	5 (8%)
50% - <75%	9 (13%)	10 (15%)
>0% - <50%	7 (10%)	7 (11%)
No decrease in OCS/lack of asthma control/ withdrawal from treatment	25 (36%)	37 (56%)
Odds ratio (95% CI)	2.39 (1.25, 4.56)	-
p-value	0.008	-
Secondary Endpoints:		
Reduction in the daily OCS dose		
At least 50% reduction in daily OCS dose from baseline, n (%)	37 (54%)	22 (33%)
Odds ratio (95% CI)	2.26 (1.10, 4.65)	-
p-value	0.027	-
Reduction to ≤5 mg/day in daily OCS dose, n (%)	37 (54%)	21 (32%)
Odds ratio (95% CI)	2.45 (1.12, 5.37)	-
p-value	0.025	-
Reduction to 0 mg/day in daily OCS dose, n (%)	10 (14%)	5 (8%)
Odds ratio (95% CI)	1.67 (0.49, 5.75)	-
p-value	0.414	-
Median Percentage Reduction in Daily OCS Dose		
Median % reduction from baseline (95% CI)	50.0 (20.0, 75.0)	0.0 (-20.0, 33.3)
Median difference (95% CI)	-30.0 (-66.7, 0.0)	
p-value	0.007	

OCS: prednisone/prednisolone

DISCUSSION:

The availability of biological agents has changed the treatment strategies for severe asthma. Initially, the availability of omalizumab changed the treatment of asthma related to IgE-mediated allergic pathogenesis⁶, and more recently, the availability of drugs targeting IL-5, which is a fundamental factor in the differentiation, activation and survival of eosinophils, changed the treatment strategy for the eosinophilic phenotype⁷. The therapeutic effect of mepolizumab, benralizumab and reslizumab is related to their capacity to bind with high affinity to IL-5 (dissociation constants in vitro of 100 and 81 pmol/L, respectively) and thus to block the interaction between IL-5 and its receptor on the surface of eosinophils⁸.

Mepolizumab is an IgG1 kappa mAb. In patients with asthma and blood eosinophil counts > 300 cells/ μ L,

dose- and time-dependent decreases in blood eosinophil counts were observed with IV mepolizumab 75 mg and SC mepolizumab 125 or 250 mg administration. However, authors concluded that the route of administration did not affect the drug exposure-response relationship. Furthermore, given that the reduction in blood eosinophils was evident as soon as three days from administration of the drug, whether SC or IV, there appears to be little significant difference in the PK-pharmacodynamics profile between the two routes of administration⁹.

The biological effects of SC mepolizumab have translated into clinical therapeutic efficacy. SC mepolizumab was associated with a significant corticosteroid-sparing effect in patients with severe eosinophilic asthma who required daily oral

corticosteroids for asthma control in the SIRIUS study¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that omalizumab is effective and safe in patients with severe allergic asthma who experience poor disease control or exacerbations despite recommended therapy.

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